

EARLY LANGUAGE LEARNING PERIOD: CHILDREN'S COGNITIVE DEVELOPMENT

Gulnora Abdullaeva Gaybulloeva

teacher of English Linguistics department,

Bukhara State University

g.g.abdullaeva@buxdu.uz

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11171743>

Abstract

Early childhood provides one of the first opportunities for language acquisition. Parents and other primary caregivers can help their children develop their brains for language development by giving them opportunities to practice new skills. The developmental milestones that indicate a child is acquiring the skills expected of them at a certain age are very important for the child's brain development. The brains of young children are reorganized after birth by the environment provided by the child. This is a process that has a long-lasting impact on their brain development by providing positive experiences for their child repeatedly.

Key words: cognitive, learning, children, language, brain, motor skills, acquisition, develop.

Professionals who work with young children as well as parents of young children anticipate the developmental milestones that indicate a child is acquiring the skills expected of them at a certain age. The development of a child's language takes precedence over motor skills during the first year of life.

The process of developing language-based communication is instinctive. Language is our most familiar method for communicating with each other, and youngsters start the cycle normally. Dr. Lise Eliot, a neurobiologist, writes: Language is instinctive due to the fact that it is largely ingrained in the brain. Our brain, along with a sophisticated vocal apparatus, evolved a complex neural circuit for rapidly perceiving, analyzing, composing, and producing language, just as we evolved neural circuits for eating and seeing (Eliot, 1999).

However, we are also aware that a child's environment's experiences are essential for language development. Our capacity for communication is the result of this interaction between nurture and nature; however, the structure of the brain is the foundation upon which language learning is built.

Neuroscientists tell us that a baby is born with millions of brain cells, which are all they will ever need. The brain is structured for language. Dendrites are appendages that branch out from each brain cell to connect it to other brain

cells. Synapses are the locations where brain cells connect. The synapse between brain cells is where electrical signals travel between brain cells.

The brain "hard-wires" a certain pattern of neural connections when synapses are repeatedly stimulated. Signals can be sent quickly and accurately thanks to this permanent, effective pathway.

This process has been confirmed by recent technological advancements in brain imaging. We can now see the physical differences between a child's brain that has been properly stimulated and one that has not because of new technology. Connections that aren't sparked by the same experiences over and over weaken or disappear. It truly is a case of "use it or lose it."

We are aware that the experiences provided by the child's environment have a significant impact on the reorganization of the connections between brain cells after birth. The child's cognitive, language, motor, and social-emotional development is greatly influenced by the parents. Parents have a long-lasting impact on their child's brain development by providing positive experiences for their child repeatedly.

Good habits, a healthy diet and regular exercises are crucial to the brain's development. Myelin, a fatty coating on brain cells, protects neural pathways and facilitates efficient signal transmission. Breast milk or properly prepared formula must provide infants with sufficient fat in their diets.

Additionally, children require a lot of sleep because proper brain development requires both deep sleep and rapid eye movement sleep. Laying out schedules for eating and resting are among very vital to help solid mental health in their youngster.

Periods of brain development that are crucial for the development of particular skills include language. The child's brain is actively forming connections for particular abilities at specific points in their development. Skills can still be learned after a window of opportunity has closed, but it will take more time and effort, despite the fact that critical periods are prime times for the development of particular neural synapses. It is during these basic periods that absence of feeling or pessimistic encounters can have the most effect.

During these times, parents can help their children develop their brains for language development by giving them opportunities to practice new skills. Language experiences without excessive stress or overstimulation are provided by day-to-day opportunities to engage in face-to-face interaction, hear language spoken, listen to the written word read aloud, and practice associating objects with words.

Early childhood provides one of the first opportunities for language acquisition. We are aware that infants are initially capable of distinguishing the sounds of all languages; however, by the time they reach the age of six months, they are no longer capable of recognizing sounds that are not heard in their native tongue. A distinct group of neurons in the auditory cortex of the brain responds to each sound that infants hear in their own language. Infants will have trouble distinguishing sounds they haven't heard often by six months of age.

Throughout life, there are opportunities for language development. While the window for adding new words never completely closes, the window for syntax or grammar is open during the preschool years and may close as early as five or six years of age.

Early language development has been documented by researchers as early as 10 weeks before birth. Through bone conduction, an infant learns the mother's voice and the sound pattern of the language she speaks before birth. After birth, a baby finds comfort in hearing his mother's voice, so a mother's lullaby can be very calming, especially if she sang to the baby while she was pregnant. A newborn is definitely able to communicate, even though he does not speak. He can investigate his dad's or alternately mother's face such that lets them know he needs to hear their voices. He can let them know when he is hungry, cold, needs his diaper changed, or has other needs that need to be met by crying.

The brain of an infant responds best to a style of speech known as "parentese," which adults use when speaking to babies naturally. Parentese uses shorter, more direct sentences, longer vowel sounds, more voice inflection, and a higher pitch than adult conversational speech. According to research, babies who hear their parents speak in parentese are more likely to associate words with the things they describe.

Parents provide the means for language acquisition. Information about brain development simply reinforces a lot of what experts in early childhood have been saying for years.

Interactions between parents and children greatly influence language development. For the baby to acquire the sounds of his native language, it is essential to read, sing, and talk to him frequently during the first year. During the first six months of a child's life, the brain begins to learn which mouth movements correspond to the sounds of speech. That is the explanation it is essential to have loads of eye to eye discussions with the child as the parent deciphers his general surroundings.

Measuring points in language development include cooing and then babbling. Babies enjoy imitating their parents. A parent not only teaches the child sound patterns but also encourages the child to take turns, which is necessary for conversation, by speaking with the child and imitating the child's sounds. By the time they were two years old, children whose parents spoke to them more frequently were able to comprehend a greater number of words and perform better on standardized tests than children whose parents did not.

When a child sees pictures in a book and simultaneously hears a parent name the pictures, the brain organizes connections for language in the second year of life. Reciting nursery rhymes, songs, and poems throughout the day can assist in language development at this age by parents and other primary caregivers.

Exercises, for example, utilizing a mirror to bring up and name facial highlights are likewise useful at this age. Before naps or bedtime, quiet, relaxed moments are ideal for reading and telling stories.

Between the ages of 24 and 35, the brain becomes more adept at creating mental representations of events, people, and things. The ability to use more words and shorter sentences is directly related to this.

There are a number of potential causes of language delays. Always consult with a professional when parents suspect such delays. In the early years, recurring ear infections delay expressive language. When a young child does not respond to sound, pulls their ears, it is always important to look for signs of an ear infection.

The child will benefit greatly from hearing two different languages spoken at home. If a child learns two languages from birth, he or she will continue to be able to understand the sounds of both languages and speak them with the same accent as a native.

It is beneficial for a child to consistently hear the same language from the parent who is its native speaker if the parents speak different languages. If, for instance, the mother speaks English fluently and the father speaks Spanish fluently, the child will be less confused if they hear each parent speak in their native tongue. The youngster might blend the dialects in their own discourse at first, yet will normally figure it out by around two and one-half years old. Then, at that point, the individual will isolate the words having a place with every language and know which language to use with which parent. The child is likely to be able to communicate fluently in both languages by the time he is seven years old, using vocabulary and grammar that are appropriate for his age.

Because she is familiar with the rules of communication, a child who enters a pre-school and is first exposed to a second language after the age of three will still be able to easily learn the language. The child will begin to comprehend the second language within three to seven months. She will be able to converse fluently after about two years. Because they still have the opportunity to learn a language, young children are more likely to learn a second language than adults. During the time the child is learning a second language, it is very important to help her build her self-confidence.

The child can learn new language words and phrases with the help of music. In addition, it is essential for parents to continue communicating with their children in her native tongue at home because doing so continues to establish the foundation for the second language by teaching the child the fundamental rules of communication. Moreover, if parents try to speak the child's second language less, the interaction between the parents and the child may suffer.

Reference:

1. Bailey, K. 2005. Practical English Language Teaching: Speaking. New York, NY: McGraw-Hill
2. Bedore, L. M., & Peña, E. D. (2008). Assessment of bilingual children for identification of language impairment: Current findings and implications for practice. *International Journal of Bilingual Education and Bilingualism*, 11(1), 1-29. doi: 10.2167/beb392.0
3. David Nunan, Caroline Linse. 2005. Practical English Language Teaching: PELT Young Learners. New York, NY: McGraw-Hill Education
4. Davies P. 2004. All aboard! 2. Oxford, UK: Macmillan Educational Publishers.
5. Dockrell, J.E. & Law, J. (2007). Measuring and understanding patterns of change in intervention studies with children. *Implications for evidence-based practice*, 1, 86- 97.
6. Dockrell, J.E. (2001). Assessing language skills in preschool children. *Child and Adolescent Mental Health*, 6, 74-86.
7. Friberg, J. C. (2010). Considerations for test selection: How do validity and reliability impact diagnostic decisions? *Child Language Teaching & Therapy*, 26(1), 77-92. doi: 10.1177/0265659009349972
8. Nicole Hahn. 2005. Assessing The Young Learners' Progress: Tests. Term Paper (Advanced seminar)
9. Abdullayeva, G. (2022). LEARNERS' PSYCHOLOGY AS ONE OF THE MAIN ISSUES INFLUENCING LANGUAGE LEARNING PROCESS. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz)*, 11(11).

- http://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/download/6321/40
13
10. Abdullayeva, G. G. (2023). LANGUAGE LEARNING AND PSYCHOLOGY. Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities, 11(2), 555-560.
<http://farspublishers.org/index.php/ijessh/article/view/520>
11. Abdullayeva, G. G. . (2023). Ways of Motivating Young Learners in EFL Classroom. Miasto Przyszłości, 32, 122–124.
<http://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/1109>
12. Rasulov , Z. (2023). LISONIY TEJAMKORLIKNING AXBOROT IFODASIDAGI ORTIQCHALIKKA MUNOSABATI. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz), 42(42). извлечено от
https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/10944
13. Rasulov, Z. I. (2023). THE NOTION OF NON-EQUIVALENT WORDS AND REALIAS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities, 11(6), 35-40.
14. Rasulov , Z. (2023). Принцип когнитивной экономии как важный фактор в передаче информации. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz), 42(42). извлечено от
https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/10954
15. Erkinovna, Y. F., Djurabaevna, D. N., & Madina, S. (2020). The Expression of Politeness Category in The Uzbek And English Languages. International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation, 24(09).
16. Erkinovna, Y. F. (2022, January). Politeness strategies. In Integration Conference on Integration of Pragmalinguistics, Functional Translation Studies and Language Teaching Processes (pp. 80-82).
17. Yuldasheva Feruza Erkinovna. (2023). Cross-Cultural Variation and Distribution of Politeness Strategies . American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education (2993-2769), 1(8), 31–34. Retrieved from <http://grnjournal.us/index.php/STEM/article/view/864>
18. Erkinovna, Y. F. . (2023). Four Current Approaches to Politeness. Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development, 2(6), 250–255. Retrieved from <http://www.bjisrd.com/index.php/bjisrd/article/view/321>
19. Yuldasheva, F. E., & Gulomov, S. (2022, January). POLITENESS LANGUAGE PATTERNS IN REQUEST. In International journal of conference series on education and social sciences (Online) (Vol. 2, No. 1). <https://ijorces.org/index.php/ojs/article/view/152>